

environment

Lichens live on every continent and every biome. They can grow on all sorts of surfaces (called substrates) such as: rock, concrete, bark, bare ground, metal, and more. Lichens do not harm the plants they grow on but they can wear away stone.

Different lichens grow in different places. The tips of tall branches will have different species on them than a rock or the shady base of a tree.

Many lichens are susceptible to air pollution. Areas with poor air quality will often have few or no lichens. They also take a very long time to grow. Many species grow less than a millimeter a year. This means it takes lichens a very long time to reestablish themselves in a place they once were.

what are lichens

Lichens are the cooperative partnership between a fungus and an alga. The body of a lichen is made of a fungus that keeps a thin layer of the algal partner inside of it. The algal partner photosynthesizes (creates energy from sunlight) and provides the fungus with nutrients.

There are over 20,000 species of lichen identified so far, with more being found every year. Lichens are named and classified according to the fungus partner and not the algae.

Cross section of a lichen: A) upper cortex B) algal layer, C) medulla, D) lower cortex, E) rhizines

Lichens are an important part of the ecosystem. They provide food, shelter, and nesting materials to animals; and they absorb pollutants and heavy metals from their environment.

LICHENS

By Eli Denzer

A quick guide to lichens and common terms

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appearance

Lichens come in many different shapes and sizes. There are several growth forms used to describe lichens (like trees, shrubs, and herbs in plants).

Crustose

Lichens lacking a bottom layer. They stick tight to the surface they grow on.

Foliose

Lobed or leaf-like; lichens that have distinct top and bottom surfaces.

Squamulose

A type of foliose lichen made up of shingles or scales, rather than interconnected lobes.

Fruticose

3-D and shrubby lichens with branches, clubs, or cups.

reproduction

Lichens can reproduce many different ways and this is important for identification. These are some of the common reproductive structures.

Soredia

Powdery loose cottony-balls of fungus and algae. These blow away to form a clone of the parent lichen.

Vegetative structures break off to grow a clone of the parent lichen.

Isidia

Finger-like or thorn-like vegetative structures that grow out of the upper surface of the lichen.

Apothecia

Usually disk shaped. Sexual reproductive structures that produce spores.

Sexual reproductive structures produce fungus spores that are different from their parent and must find their own algal partner.

Lirellate apothecia

Special long and squished apothecia. They may be straight, curved, or branched. Characteristic of the genus *Graphis*.

colors

The color of each part of the lichen is due to chemicals produced by the fungus. Many are stored as tiny crystals. These chemicals serve important functions like sunscreen.

Uppersurface color

The main color of the lichen. Can change depending on moisture

When a lichen gets wet the upper surface becomes more transparent, making the green of the algae more visible.

Cilia

Eyelash-like hairs on lobe edges.

Underside color

Color of the lower surface a foliose lichen. Common colors are white or black with brown edges.

Medulla

The inside layer of a lichen. It is usually white. But not always!

Rhizines

Root-like anchors on the underside of lobes.